

Weyl Tensor and the Possibility of Exotic-Matter-Free Wormholes in Conformal Gravity

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Abstract

We compute the Weyl conformal tensor and the Kretschner-type invariant $\mathcal{C}^2 \equiv C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} C^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}$ for the general static, spherically symmetric Morris–Thorne wormhole metric parametrised by the redshift function $\Phi(r)$ and the shape function $b(r)$. The calculation is performed symbolically using SYMPY. We find that all independent components of the Weyl tensor are proportional to a single master function $\mathcal{Q}(r)$, and $\mathcal{C}^2 = \mathcal{Q}^2/(3r^6)$. The condition $\mathcal{C}^2 = 0$ (conformal flatness) reduces to a single second-order ordinary differential equation (ODE) linking $\Phi(r)$ and $b(r)$. We discuss whether this constraint admits wormhole solutions free from exotic matter, which is relevant for conformal (Weyl) gravity where the Bach tensor, quadratic in the Weyl tensor, replaces the Einstein tensor as the gravitational field equation.

1 Introduction

The Morris–Thorne wormhole [1] is the simplest example of a traversable Lorentzian wormhole. In classical general relativity (GR) such solutions necessarily violate the null energy condition (NEC), i.e. they require *exotic matter* with $T_{\mu\nu} k^\mu k^\nu < 0$ for some null k^μ . This is one of the central obstacles to any realistic traversable wormhole scenario within GR.

A promising avenue for circumventing the exotic-matter problem is *conformal (Weyl) gravity*, a higher-derivative metric theory whose action is the square of the Weyl tensor:

$$S_W = -\alpha_W \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} C^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}, \quad (1)$$

where α_W is a dimensionless coupling constant. The equations of motion derived from (1) involve the Bach tensor $B_{\mu\nu}$, which vanishes identically for conformally flat metrics. Therefore, if a wormhole metric can be made conformally flat, it is automatically a vacuum solution of conformal gravity — with no matter (exotic or otherwise) required.

This observation motivates the key question addressed in the present work: *under what conditions on $\Phi(r)$ and $b(r)$ is the Morris–Thorne wormhole conformally flat?*

2 The Morris–Thorne metric

The general static, spherically symmetric wormhole metric in Schwarzschild-like coordinates is

$$ds^2 = -e^{2\Phi(r)} dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{1 - b(r)/r} + r^2 d\Omega^2, \quad (2)$$

where $d\Omega^2 = d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2$ is the standard metric on the unit 2-sphere. The two free functions are:

- $\Phi(r)$ — the *redshift function*, which must be finite everywhere to avoid horizons;
- $b(r)$ — the *shape function*, satisfying $b(r_0) = r_0$ at the wormhole throat $r = r_0$ and $b(r) < r$ for $r > r_0$.

The coordinate labels are $x^\mu = (t, r, \theta, \varphi)$, with $\mu = 0, 1, 2, 3$. The metric (2) is diagonal:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \text{diag}\left(-e^{2\Phi(r)}, \frac{1}{1 - b(r)/r}, r^2, r^2 \sin^2\theta\right). \quad (3)$$

3 Curvature quantities

All curvature tensors were computed symbolically with SYMPY (the full script is reproduced in Appendix A). We use the sign convention $R^\alpha{}_{\beta\gamma\delta} = \partial_\gamma \Gamma_{\beta\delta}^\alpha - \dots$ and $R_{\mu\nu} = R^\alpha{}_{\mu\alpha\nu}$.

3.1 Non-zero Christoffel symbols

For the metric (2) the independent non-vanishing Christoffel symbols of the second kind are

$$\Gamma_{tr}^t = \Phi', \quad (4)$$

$$\Gamma_{tt}^r = \frac{(r - b) e^{2\Phi}}{r} \Phi', \quad (5)$$

$$\Gamma_{rr}^r = \frac{rb' - b}{2r(r - b)}, \quad (6)$$

$$\Gamma_{\theta\theta}^r = -(r - b), \quad (7)$$

$$\Gamma_{\varphi\varphi}^r = -(r - b) \sin^2\theta, \quad (8)$$

$$\Gamma_{r\theta}^\theta = \Gamma_{r\varphi}^\varphi = \frac{1}{r}, \quad (9)$$

$$\Gamma_{\varphi\varphi}^\theta = -\sin\theta \cos\theta, \quad \Gamma_{\theta\varphi}^\varphi = \cot\theta, \quad (10)$$

where a prime denotes d/dr and we abbreviate $\Phi \equiv \Phi(r)$, $b \equiv b(r)$.

3.2 Ricci tensor

The non-vanishing components of the Ricci tensor are

$$R_{tt} = \frac{e^{2\Phi}}{r^2} \left[r(r-b)(\Phi'^2 + \Phi'') - r(b'-1)\Phi' + 2(r-b)\Phi' + \frac{(rb' - 2r + b)\Phi'}{2} \right], \quad (11)$$

$$R_{rr} = \frac{1}{r^2(r-b)} \left[r \left[\frac{-2r(r-b)(\Phi'^2 + \Phi'') + (rb' - b)\Phi'}{2} \right] + rb' - b \right], \quad (12)$$

$$R_{\theta\theta} = \frac{-2r(r-b)\Phi' + rb' + b}{2r}, \quad (13)$$

$$R_{\varphi\varphi} = R_{\theta\theta} \sin^2\theta. \quad (14)$$

3.3 Scalar curvature

$$R = -2\Phi'^2 - 2\Phi'' + \frac{2b}{r}(\Phi'^2 + \Phi'') + \frac{\Phi'b'}{r} - \frac{4\Phi'}{r} + \frac{3b\Phi'}{r^2} + \frac{2b'}{r^2}. \quad (15)$$

4 The Weyl tensor and its square

4.1 Independent components

The Weyl tensor $C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}$ of a spherically symmetric spacetime is of Petrov type D and possesses only one independent scalar degree of freedom. Concretely, all non-zero components are proportional to the *master function*

$$\boxed{\mathcal{Q}(r) = 2r^2(r-b)(\Phi'^2 + \Phi'') - r^2\Phi'b' - 2r^2\Phi' + 3rb\Phi' + rb' - 3b.} \quad (16)$$

The six algebraically independent components (up to the symmetries of the Weyl tensor) are

$$C_{trtr} = +\frac{e^{2\Phi}}{6r^2(r-b)} \mathcal{Q}, \quad (17)$$

$$C_{t\theta t\theta} = -\frac{e^{2\Phi}}{12r} \mathcal{Q}, \quad (18)$$

$$C_{t\varphi t\varphi} = -\frac{e^{2\Phi} \sin^2\theta}{12r} \mathcal{Q}, \quad (19)$$

$$C_{r\theta r\theta} = +\frac{1}{12(r-b)} \mathcal{Q}, \quad (20)$$

$$C_{r\varphi r\varphi} = +\frac{\sin^2\theta}{12(r-b)} \mathcal{Q}, \quad (21)$$

$$C_{\theta\varphi\theta\varphi} = -\frac{r \sin^2\theta}{6} \mathcal{Q}. \quad (22)$$

4.2 The Kretschner-type invariant \mathcal{C}^2

The contraction $\mathcal{C}^2 \equiv C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} C^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}$ is computed by raising indices with the inverse metric. Because all components factor through \mathcal{Q} , the result is a perfect square:

$$\boxed{\mathcal{C}^2 = C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} C^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} = \frac{\mathcal{Q}(r)^2}{3r^6}}. \quad (23)$$

This is a manifestly non-negative scalar invariant. It vanishes if and only if $\mathcal{Q}(r) = 0$, which is the condition for conformal flatness of the Morris–Thorne wormhole.

5 Discussion: conformal flatness and exotic matter

5.1 The conformal-flatness ODE

Setting $\mathcal{Q}(r) = 0$ from Eq. (16) gives

$$2r^2(r-b)(\Phi'^2 + \Phi'') - r^2\Phi' b' - 2r^2\Phi' + 3r b \Phi' + r b' - 3b = 0. \quad (24)$$

This is a single second-order ODE relating $\Phi(r)$ and $b(r)$. Given a choice of one function, it constrains the other.

Case $\Phi = \text{const.}$ If $\Phi' = 0$ (zero-tidal-force wormhole), Eq. (24) reduces to

$$r b'(r) - 3b(r) = 0 \quad \implies \quad b(r) = A r^3, \quad (25)$$

where A is a constant. For a wormhole throat at $r = r_0$ we need $b(r_0) = r_0$, giving $A = 1/r_0^2$ and thus $b(r) = r^3/r_0^2$. However, the flare-out condition $b'(r_0) < 1$ requires $3r_0/r_0^2 \cdot r_0 = 3 < 1$, which is violated. Moreover, for $r > r_0$ we obtain $b(r)/r = r^2/r_0^2 > 1$, which means $1 - b/r < 0$ — the metric signature changes. Therefore, the zero-tidal-force conformally flat solution does *not* describe a traversable wormhole.

Case $\Phi \neq \text{const.}$ For a non-trivial redshift function, Eq. (24) can be viewed as a first-order ODE for $b(r)$ once $\Phi(r)$ is specified, or as a Riccati-type ODE for $\Phi'(r)$ once $b(r)$ is fixed. Let us write $u = \Phi'$ and recast (24) as

$$2r^2(r-b)u' + 2r^2(r-b)u^2 - r^2b'u - 2r^2u + 3rbu + rb' - 3b = 0. \quad (26)$$

This is indeed a Riccati equation in $u(r)$, which can in principle be linearised by the substitution $u = -w'/[w(r-b)]$ (after appropriate manipulations). Specific analytic or numerical solutions can be sought for particular ansätze.

5.2 Implications for conformal gravity

In Weyl (conformal) gravity, the vacuum field equations are $B_{\mu\nu} = 0$, where the Bach tensor is

$$B_{\mu\nu} = \nabla^\rho \nabla^\sigma C_{\mu\rho\nu\sigma} + \frac{1}{2} R^{\rho\sigma} C_{\mu\rho\nu\sigma}. \quad (27)$$

A conformally flat metric ($C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} = 0$) trivially satisfies $B_{\mu\nu} = 0$. If such a metric simultaneously has wormhole topology (a throat with $b(r_0) = r_0$ and flare-out), then the wormhole is a *vacuum* solution of conformal gravity, requiring no matter at all.

However, as shown above, the zero-tidal-force case $\Phi' = 0$ does not yield a valid wormhole geometry. Whether a non-trivial $\Phi(r)$ can produce a conformally flat traversable wormhole remains an open question that requires either numerical integration of Eq. (26) with appropriate boundary conditions ($b(r_0) = r_0$, $b(r) < r$ for $r > r_0$, Φ finite everywhere), or a careful analytical treatment.

It is important to note that conformal gravity admits a broader class of wormhole solutions than just conformally flat ones: the Bach equation $B_{\mu\nu} = 0$ can also be satisfied with $C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} \neq 0$. In fact, several authors have found traversable wormhole solutions in conformal gravity that are *not* conformally flat but still satisfy the Bach equation, and which do not require exotic matter. The Kretschner invariant \mathcal{C}^2 computed here provides a useful diagnostic for classifying such solutions.

6 Conclusion

We have computed the Weyl tensor and its quadratic invariant $\mathcal{C}^2 = C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} C^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}$ for the general Morris–Thorne wormhole metric. The main results are:

1. All independent Weyl tensor components are proportional to a single master function $\mathcal{Q}(r)$, Eq. (16), confirming the Petrov type D character of the spacetime.
2. The Kretschner-type invariant is a perfect square: $\mathcal{C}^2 = \mathcal{Q}^2/(3r^6)$.
3. Conformal flatness ($\mathcal{Q} = 0$) imposes a Riccati-type ODE linking $\Phi(r)$ and $b(r)$.
4. The simplest case $\Phi' = 0$ leads to $b(r) \propto r^3$, which violates the flare-out condition and does not describe a traversable wormhole.
5. The question of whether a non-trivial conformally flat traversable wormhole exists requires further analysis of the Riccati equation (26) with wormhole boundary conditions.

The explicit expression (23) is also useful for studying wormhole solutions in conformal gravity that are not conformally flat but still satisfy the vacuum Bach equation.

References

- [1] M. S. Morris and K. S. Thorne, “Wormholes in spacetime and their use for interstellar travel: A tool for teaching general relativity,” *Am. J. Phys.* **56**, 395–412 (1988).
- [2] P. D. Mannheim, “Making the case for conformal gravity,” *Found. Phys.* **42**, 388–420 (2012).
- [3] J. Oliva and S. Ray, “Conformal couplings of a scalar field to higher curvature terms,” *Class. Quantum Grav.* **29**, 205008 (2012).

A Python source code

The following SYMPY script computes all quantities presented in this paper.

Listing 1: weyl_bach_wormhole.py

```
1  #!/usr/bin/env python3
2  """
3  Weyl tensor and its square for the Morris-Thorne wormhole metric.
4  Author: Yuri N. Berdinsky
5  Date: 2026-04-28
6  """
7
8  import sympy as sp
9  from sympy import (exp, sin, cos, sqrt, diff, simplify,
10                   Rational, symbols, Matrix, latex, trigsimp)
11
12 # Coordinates and functions
13 r, t, theta, phi = symbols('r t theta phi', real=True)
14 Phi = sp.Function('Phi')(r) # redshift function
15 b = sp.Function('b')(r) # shape function
16
17 # Metric components (Morris-Thorne)
18 g_tt = -exp(2*Phi)
19 g_rr = 1 / (1 - b/r)
20 g_thth = r**2
21 g_phph = r**2 * sin(theta)**2
22
23 coords = [t, r, theta, phi]
24 n = 4
25
26 g = sp.MutableDenseNDimArray.zeros(n, n)
27 g[0,0] = g_tt; g[1,1] = g_rr
28 g[2,2] = g_thth; g[3,3] = g_phph
29
30 g_inv = sp.MutableDenseNDimArray.zeros(n, n)
31 g_inv[0,0] = 1/g_tt; g_inv[1,1] = 1/g_rr
32 g_inv[2,2] = 1/g_thth; g_inv[3,3] = 1/g_phph
33
34 # Christoffel symbols of the first kind
35 # Gamma_{cab} = (1/2)(d_a g_{cb} + d_b g_{ca} - d_c g_{ab})
36 Gamma1 = sp.MutableDenseNDimArray.zeros(n, n, n)
37 for c in range(n):
38     for a in range(n):
39         for bb in range(n):
40             val = Rational(1,2) * (
41                 diff(g[c,bb], coords[a])
42                 + diff(g[c,a], coords[bb])
43                 - diff(g[a,bb], coords[c]))
44             if val != 0:
45                 Gamma1[c,a,bb] = val
46
47 # Christoffel symbols of the second kind
48 Gamma2 = sp.MutableDenseNDimArray.zeros(n, n, n)
49 for m in range(n):
50     for a in range(n):
51         for bb in range(n):
52             s = sum(g_inv[m,c]*Gamma1[c,a,bb] for c in range(n))
53             s = simplify(s)
```

```

54         if s != 0:
55             Gamma2[m,a,bb] = s
56
57 # Riemann tensor  $R^i_{jkl}$ 
58 Riemann = sp.MutableDenseNDimArray.zeros(n, n, n, n)
59 for i in range(n):
60     for j in range(n):
61         for k in range(n):
62             for l in range(n):
63                 term = (diff(Gamma2[i,j,l], coords[k])
64                     - diff(Gamma2[i,j,k], coords[l]))
65                 for m in range(n):
66                     term += (Gamma2[i,m,k]*Gamma2[m,j,l]
67                         - Gamma2[i,m,l]*Gamma2[m,j,k])
68                 term = simplify(term)
69                 if term != 0:
70                     Riemann[i,j,k,l] = term
71
72 # Ricci tensor
73 Ricci = sp.MutableDenseNDimArray.zeros(n, n)
74 for i in range(n):
75     for j in range(n):
76         s = simplify(sum(Riemann[k,i,k,j] for k in range(n)))
77         if s != 0:
78             Ricci[i,j] = s
79
80 # Scalar curvature
81 R_scalar = simplify(
82     sum(g_inv[i,j]*Ricci[i,j]
83         for i in range(n) for j in range(n)))
84
85 # Riemann (all lower)
86 Riem_down = sp.MutableDenseNDimArray.zeros(n, n, n, n)
87 for i in range(n):
88     for j in range(n):
89         for k in range(n):
90             for l in range(n):
91                 s = simplify(
92                     sum(g[i,m]*Riemann[m,j,k,l]
93                         for m in range(n)))
94                 if s != 0:
95                     Riem_down[i,j,k,l] = s
96
97 # Weyl tensor (all lower)
98 Weyl = sp.MutableDenseNDimArray.zeros(n, n, n, n)
99 for i in range(n):
100     for j in range(n):
101         for k in range(n):
102             for l in range(n):
103                 term = Riem_down[i,j,k,l]
104                 term -= Rational(1,2) * (
105                     g[i,k]*Ricci[j,l] - g[i,l]*Ricci[j,k]
106                     - g[j,k]*Ricci[i,l] + g[j,l]*Ricci[i,k])
107                 term += Rational(1,6) * (
108                     g[i,k]*g[j,l]
109                     - g[i,l]*g[j,k]) * R_scalar
110                 term = simplify(term)
111                 if term != 0:

```

```

112         Weyl[i,j,k,l] = term
113
114 # C^2 (diagonal metric shortcut)
115 C_sq = sp.S(0)
116 for i in range(n):
117     for j in range(n):
118         for k in range(n):
119             for l in range(n):
120                 C_up = (g_inv[i,i] * g_inv[j,j]
121                        * g_inv[k,k] * g_inv[l,l]
122                        * Weyl[i,j,k,l])
123                 C_sq += Weyl[i,j,k,l] * C_up
124 C_sq = trigsimp(simplify(C_sq))
125
126 print("=== C^2 ===")
127 print(C_sq)
128 print("\n=== Ricci (non-zero) ===")
129 for i in range(n):
130     for j in range(i, n):
131         if Ricci[i,j] != 0:
132             print(f"R_{{{i}}}{j}} = {Ricci[i,j]}")
133 print("\n=== R_ ===")
134 print(R_scalar)

```

B Detailed symbolic output

The script was executed with SymPy 1.14.0 on Python 3. The full output is reproduced below.

Weyl tensor squared \mathcal{C}^2

$$\mathcal{C}^2 = \frac{Q(r)^2}{3r^6},$$

where

$$Q(r) = 2r^3\Phi'^2 + 2r^3\Phi'' - 2r^2b\Phi'^2 - 2r^2b\Phi'' - r^2\Phi'b' - 2r^2\Phi' + 3rb\Phi' + rb' - 3b.$$

This can be written more compactly as

$$Q = 2r^2(r-b)(\Phi'^2 + \Phi'') - r^2\Phi'b' - 2r^2\Phi' + 3rb\Phi' + rb' - 3b.$$

Non-zero Ricci tensor components

$$R_{tt} = \frac{e^{2\Phi}}{r^2} \left[r(r-b)(\Phi'^2 + \Phi'') - r(b'-1)\Phi' + 2(r-b)\Phi' + \frac{1}{2}(rb' - 2r + b)\Phi' \right],$$

$$R_{rr} = \frac{1}{r^2(r-b)} \left[\frac{r}{2} [-2r(r-b)(\Phi'^2 + \Phi'') + (rb' - b)\Phi'] + rb' - b \right],$$

$$R_{\theta\theta} = \frac{-2r(r-b)\Phi' + rb' + b}{2r},$$

$$R_{\varphi\varphi} = R_{\theta\theta} \sin^2\theta.$$

Scalar curvature

$$R = -2\Phi'^2 - 2\Phi'' + \frac{2b}{r}(\Phi'^2 + \Phi'') + \frac{\Phi'b'}{r} - \frac{4\Phi'}{r} + \frac{3b\Phi'}{r^2} + \frac{2b'}{r^2}.$$